

Circulation Pump Power for Solar Water Heater

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Abstract

This publication introduces calculations of circulation pump power for solar water heater, forced circulation system. The theoretical power is estimated as 0.5 Watt, while the nominal power of the relevant pump is 6 Watt. Energy consumption of such pump is 25 kWh/year. The required water flow is 2 liters/minute and the pump's head is 1.5 meter.

The publication determines, step by step, water flow, pressure drop in solar collector and pipes, and theoretical power of circulation pump.

Calculations are for solar water heater for residential unit located 9 floors from the solar collector on building's roof. The size of the solar water heater is 150 liters storage tank and 6,150 kcal/day collector.

Excessive power of circulation pump increases water flow and decreases stratification in storage tank with negative impact on solar collector's efficiency and energy losses in circulation pipes. Therefore the power and specifications of circulation pump must be carefully determined.

Introduction

Solar water heaters (SWH) must be installed in new buildings in Israel according to the law. They save 5 % of the national electricity consumption [3] and are important component of the Israeli economy and standard of living. Solar law requires SWH for buildings up to 27 meters high considering available space on the roof of the building and energy losses for longer piping.

This work is for forced circulation system, using circulation pump and differential thermostat. It is based on other publications related to solar water heaters [1], [2].

Usually thermosyphonic installations are up to 4 floors from roof, and for lower floors, up to 9 floors from roof, forced circulation systems are applied.

The calculations are for SWH for residential unit located 9 floors from the solar collector on building's roof. The size of the SWH is 150 liters storage tank and 6,150 kcal/day collector.

All conditions are for Israel so the results do not necessary apply to other countries.

Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as energy unit. In this work the energy unit is kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal.

Application of kcal instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference indicates immediately the amount of energy in kcal.

Electric energy is expressed in kWh.

1 kWh is 859.85 kcal and 1 kcal is 1.1630 Wh.

Solar Water Heater

Solar water heater (SWH) analyzed in this work is forced circulation open system. "Open" means without heat exchanger. The water circulating between solar collector and storage tank is city water under city water pressure.

Solar legislation in Israel distinguishes between vertical and horizontal storage tank [3]. In this work vertical storage tank is considered.

The system may include one solar collector or few collectors, in both cases this work defines the collector(s) array as a "collector".

Main components of SWH:

- Solar collector
- Storage tank
- Circulation pump
- Differential thermostat
- Circulation pipes

Solar legislation in Israel requires installation of solar water heater in new buildings up to 9 floors, 27 meters from roof [3].

This work is for SWH located 9 floors under roof with 150 liters storage tank. Two type of pipes are considered: 1/2" steel pipe and 16 mm OD plastic pipe. Each floor is regarded as 3 meters high (gross), resulting in 6 meters of circulation pipes. In addition 6 meters of circulation pipe is estimated to be located on roof (2 pipes 3 meters each) and 6 meters of circulation pipe in residential unit (2 pipes 3 meters each).

Circulation pump should be located in the lowest and the coldest point of the system, which is outlet pipe from storage tank in direction to solar collector.

Circulation Pipes Length

There are 2 circulation pipes, one supplying hot water from solar collector to storage tank and the second returning the water from the storage tank to the collector.

It is assumed that the circulation is during all solar hours.

The media in the pipes is city water under the city water pressure, heated by the solar collector. The media in pipes, collector and storage tank is the same city water under city water pressure.

Solar collector is located on roof and storage tank is located in the residential unit.

This work considers the following length of circulation pipes:

- 6 meters (3 meters in each direction) on roof
- 6 meters (3 meters in each direction) for each floor
- 6 meters (3 meters in each direction) in the residential unit

Water Flow in Circulation Pipes

The initial estimation of water flow in circulation pipes will be based on 10°C temperature difference between input and output temperature of the solar collector at maximum radiation.

Maximum solar radiation in Jerusalem is 861 kcal/m², hr in June noon.

Publication [1] describes procedure for calculations of solar collector's energy based on solar radiation. Application of this procedure results in 1,203 kcal/hr collector's energy.

Formula 1 - Energy required to heat water

The formula can be found in publication [1] Section "Storage Tank Average Temperature".

$$E = m * c * \Delta t$$

$$E/\text{Time} = (m / \text{Time}) * c * \Delta t$$

$$E/\text{Time} = Q$$

$$m / \text{Time} = \rho * V$$

$$Q = \rho * V * c * \Delta t$$

E	energy to heat the mass of water [kcal]
m	mass of water [kg]
c	specific heat of water = 1 [kcal/kg, °C]
Δt	temperature difference [°C]
Q	energy in period of time, solar collector's energy [kcal/hr]
ρ	density of water = 1 [kg/liter]
V	water flow [liter/hr]

Specific heat of water c is 1 kcal/kg,°C

$$Q \text{ [kcal/hr]} = V \text{ [liter/hr]} * \Delta t \text{ [°C]} * 1 \text{ [kcal/kg,°C]} * 1 \text{ [kg/liter]}$$

$$Q = V * \Delta t$$

Formula 2 - Maximum water flow required

$$V \text{ [liter/hr]} = Q \text{ [kcal/hr]} / \Delta t$$

Considering 10°C temperature difference between input and output to solar collector, the maximum flow is:

$$\begin{aligned} V \text{ [liter/hr]} &= 1,203 \text{ [kcal/hr]} / 10 \text{ [°C]} \\ &= 120.3 \text{ L/hr} = 2 \text{ L/min} \end{aligned}$$

The initial water flow in circulation pipes is calculated as 2 L/min. This will be changed in the following paragraphs according to the available circulation pumps.

Water Stratification

Water stratification is very important feature of solar water heaters.

For example, if the stratification is 10°C temperature difference and the temperature on top of the storage tank is 40°C and at the bottom 30°C, mixing all water in the storage tank will result in average temperature of 35°C, which is useless (too cold) for shower. Therefore it is very important to keep the stratification as high as possible. Vertical storage tanks have much better stratification than horizontal storage tanks. Solar legislation in Israel requires bigger solar collector for horizontal storage tank [3].

It is very important that the water temperature at the entrance to solar collector will be as low as possible. This improves the solar collector's efficiency and results in more energy available for use. To achieve the lowest temperature as possible at the entrance to solar collector, water stratification in storage tank should be as high as possible, which will result in cold, unheated water at the bottom of the storage tank, from there the circulation pump will transfer it the solar collector. In addition, lower is the water temperature at the bottom of the storage tank, lower are the energy losses from the circulation pipes.

Excessive power of the circulation pump increases circulation water flow and decreases stratification in storage tank with negative impact on solar collector's efficiency and energy losses in circulation pipes. Therefore the power and specification of circulation pump must be carefully determined.

Circulation Pipes Pressure Drop

Following pressure drop components will be considered for the calculations:

- Solar collector
- Storage tank input/output
- Bends
- Pipe's length

Solar Collector Pressure Drop

Solar legislation in Israel determines size of SWH, size of storage tank and size of solar collector, in relation to residential unit size. Solar collect size is not expressed in square meters but in standard kilocalories per day. Detailed procedure to determine the solar collector size in standard kilocalories per day may be found in publication [3]. Residential unit considered in this work is 4 rooms unit which requires 150 liters storage tank and 6,150 kcal/day solar collector.

The most popular SWH in Israel is Chromagen.

Chromagen CR11 solar collector is in size 6,169 kcal/day. Description of Chromagen solar collector can be found in publication [4].

The solar collector comes with 10 risers which are copper pipes 8 mm or 16 mm OD, 1700 mm long, connected to 22/28 mm OD copper manifolds.

8mm OD risers are for closed systems with heat exchanger, while open systems need larger tubes to prevent blocking by scale. 16 mm OD risers and 28 mm OD manifolds will be considered for calculation.

The dimensions of Chromagen solar collector [4] are 1,820 mm height and 1,270 mm wide.

Solar Collector's Riser

There are 10 risers. The flow will be equally divided between them:

$$V_1 = V / 10 = 2 \text{ L/min} / 10 = 0.2 \text{ L/min}$$

Table 1 - Solar collector's riser and manifolds dimensions

riser OD	15.88	mm
Thickness	1.24	mm
riser dia In	13.39	mm
riser length	1.70	m
manifold OD	28.58	mm
Thickness	1.65	mm
manifold dia In	25.27	mm
manifold length	1.40	m

Riser diameter is 16 mm OD, inside diameter is 13.4 mm. Maximum roughness for used copper pipe is 0.03 mm.

According to the Pressure Drop Online-Calculator [5], the pressure drop of riser is 0.00007 bar (0.07 mbar). This value includes inlet and outlet pressure drop.

Solar Collector's Manifold

Manifold is 28 mm OD, 25.3 mm inside diameter.

Pressure drop of manifold is caused mostly because of risers' connections. Single manifold pressure drop is 0.15 mbar, and both manifolds 0.30 mbar

Table 2 - Pressure drop of solar collector

Collector riser	0.07	mbar
Manifold	0.05	mbar
Risers entrance x10	0.10	mbar
2 manifolds	0.30	mbar
Pipe to collector	0.31	mbar
Collector to pipe	0.28	mbar
Σ Solar collector	0.96	mbar
Σ Solar collector	0.001	bar

The pressure drop in storage tank is caused by connections of both pipes.

Table 3 - Pressure drop storage tank

Pipe to tank	0.31	mbar
Tank to pipe	0.28	mbar
Σ Tank	0.59	mbar
Σ Tank	0.001	bar

There are 4 bends for connections to solar collector and storage tank. In addition, 20 bends are considered in various places on roof and apartment, but not between floors.

There are different bends for steel pipe and plastic pipe. Steel pipe pressure drop is lower because bigger inside diameter.

Table 4 - Pressure drop on bends

		Steel	XLPE
4 bends	mbar	7.60	7.60
20 bends	mbar	3.80	14.40
Σ	mbar	11.40	22.00

As mentioned before pressure drop is different for steel and plastic pipes. Roughness of steel pipes is considered 4 mm (maximum for steel) and for plastic 0.03 mm (maximum for plastic). Despite very big difference in roughness, steel pipe pressure drop is lower because of bigger diameter.

Table 5 - Pressure drop in circulation pipes on roof and in apartment

		Steel	XLPE
12 meters on roof and in apartment	mbar	15.82	22.33

The length of 12 meters is double pipe 3 meters on roof and 3 meters in apartment.

Table 6 - Total pipe's length pressure drop without floors

		Steel	XLPE
Solar collector	mbar	0.96	0.96
Storage tank	mbar	0.59	0.59
4 bends	mbar	7.60	7.60
20 bends	mbar	3.80	14.40
12 meters roof and apartment	mbar	15.82	22.33
Σ	mbar	28.77	45.88
Σ	bar	0.029	0.046

Table 7 - Each floor pipe's length pressure drop

		Steel	XLPE
1 floor 6 meters	Mbar	7.91	11.16
1 floor 6 meters	Bar	0.008	0.011

The calculations are for 9 floors below the roof. Each floor is 3 meters high, which means 6 meters of straight pipe for each floor.

Table 8 - Total circulation pipe pressure drop

		Steel	XLPE
Solar collector	mbar	0.96	0.96
Storage tank	mbar	0.59	0.59
Bends	mbar	11.40	22.00
12 meters roof and apartment	mbar	15.82	22.33
9 floors	mbar	71.19	100.44
Σ	mbar	99.96	146.32
Σ	bar	0.100	0.146

Circulation Pump Power

Formula for pump power may be found in publication [6]:

Formula 3 - Pump power

$$P \text{ [kW]} = V \text{ [m}^3\text{/hr]} * \rho \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]} * g \text{ [m/s}^2\text{]} * H \text{ [m]} / (3.6 * 10^6)$$

- P pump power 100% efficient [kW]
- V water flow [m³/hr]
- ρ density [kg/m³]
- g gravity = 9.80665 m/s²
- H head, pressure drop [m]

Table 9 - Pump power

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Water flow	V	2.0058	L/min
Water flow	V	120.347163	L/hr
Water flow	V	0.1203	m ³ /hr
Density of water	ρ	1	kg/L
Density of water	ρ	1,000	kg/m ³
Gravity	G	9.80665	m/s ²
Pressure drop	H	0.146	Bar
Bar to m		10.1974429	bar/m
Pressure drop	H	1.492	M
Pump power	P	0.00048916	kW
Pump power	P	0.49	W

The pump required is H=1.5 m, V=2 L/min.

The smallest circulation pump that can be found on Internet is 5.4 W, Ave flow = 1.5 L/min, Ave H=0.75 m. This pump is too small. This pump is for 105°C, however it is for closed circulation as it is not for city water pressure of 10 bar. The pump efficiency is 3%.

The smallest pumps for open circulation SWH can be found on Internet as references [7] [8] [9].

Reference [9] does not mention pump's power, but has the same specification as reference [8], therefore the same nominal power will be applied.

Table 10 - Available circulation pumps

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	[7]	[8]	[9]
Ave Flow	V	L/min	8.2	3.2	3.2
Ave Head	H	M	1.2	1.5	1.5
Calculated power	P	W	1.6	0.8	0.8
Actual power	PA	W	10	6	6
Efficiency	ETA		16%	13%	13%

Pumps from reference [8] and [9] are the smallest pumps with required characteristics, and they will be applied for further calculations.

Electricity Consumption for Circulation Pump

The circulation pump is operating only in solar hours. Actually differential thermostat stops the pump at time of balance between SWH's losses and the available solar energy.

Calculations of time of balance may be found in publication [1] Section "Time of Balance – Balance Hour".

Table 11 - Circulation pump operating hours

Month	Sunrise	Sunset	Balance time	HRcirc hr/d
1	06:39	16:57	16:12	9.6
2	06:21	17:25	16:46	10.4
3	05:49	17:47	17:14	11.4
4	06:10	19:08	18:41	12.5
5	05:42	19:28	19:07	13.4
6	05:33	19:46	19:31	14.0
7	05:44	19:45	19:24	13.7
8	06:03	19:22	18:55	12.9
9	06:23	18:44	18:11	11.8
10	06:42	18:06	17:27	10.8
11	06:07	16:39	15:54	9.8
12	06:31	16:36	15:46	9.3

Table 12 - Electricity consumption of circulation pump

Month	HRcirc hr/d	Calculated		Actual	
		E pump kWh/d	E pump kWh/month	E pump kWh/d	E pump kWh/month
1	9.6	0.0047	0.15	0.0574	1.78
2	10.4	0.0051	0.14	0.0626	1.75
3	11.4	0.0056	0.17	0.0686	2.13
4	12.5	0.0061	0.18	0.0751	2.25
5	13.4	0.0066	0.20	0.0805	2.50
6	14.0	0.0068	0.20	0.0838	2.51
7	13.7	0.0067	0.21	0.0820	2.54
8	12.9	0.0063	0.20	0.0772	2.39
9	11.8	0.0058	0.17	0.0709	2.13
10	10.8	0.0053	0.16	0.0646	2.00
11	9.8	0.0048	0.14	0.0588	1.76
12	9.3	0.0045	0.14	0.0555	1.72
Σ kWh/y			2.08		25.47
Ave			0.17		2.12

Energy consumption of circulation pump for solar water heater with storage tank 150 liter located 9 floors under roof is 25.5 kWh/year.

Calculations' Results

The results are for plastic pipe 11.6 mm inside diameter, 9 floors from roof.

Table 13 - Calculations results

Parameter	Unit	Calculated	Actual
Water flow	L/min	2.0	3.2
Pressure drop	m	1.5	1.5
Pump efficiency		100%	13%
Pump power	Watt	0.5	6
Pump electricity consumption	kWh/y	2.1	25.5

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